

Towards Network Time CMCs

Carsten Rieck

Measurement Technology, Time and Optics
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
Borås, Sweden
carsten.rieck@ri.se

Yan Xie

VSL National Metrology Institute of the Netherlands
Delft, The Netherlands

Tapio Lehtonen

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
Espoo, Finland

Summary— Calibration methods for PTP are presented that eventually will be qualified as Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMC) and consequently describe a NMI’s capability to calibrate PTP networks or endpoints. The methods are currently geared towards the PTP profiles used for digital substation environments but can also be useful for calibration of other timing protocols such as NTP.

Keywords—CMC; PTP; IEE1588; calibration; traceability; digital substation; IEC 61850-9-2

I. INTRODUCTION

Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMC) are reviewed documentation of NMIs or DIs necessary in the formal traceability to the SI system. Where traditional time metrology is mostly concerned with micro-wave domain signals with methods for frequency, time and time interval, measuring sinusoidal or pulses in matched coaxial distribution systems, the calibration of message based time distribution is slightly outside of common practice. Few NMIs have CMCs that address the calibration of network devices or services.

In this paper the metrology of time transfer using Ethernet based communications is introduced. Focus is on IEEE1588 based synchronization [1,2], which is important for an increasing number of applications, especially in power distribution or communication synchronization. The background to this work is the project Digital-IT – EPM Metrology for Digital Substation Instrumentation 21NRM02/n01 [3], which has the overall objective “to develop methodology for calibration of merging unit phase displacement under PTPv2 synchronicity”. The application requires robust and reliable timing and sampled values (SV) communications, with PTP timing better than 100 ns uncertainty within a substation.

The digital substation environment in accordance with IEC 61850 family of standards is a popular choice in substation design connecting parts of the transmission and distribution grids. Initial recommendations around 2004 of the IEC 61850-9-2 standard for synchronization of digital substation timing [4] suggest 1PPS signals provided by coaxial or optical signal distributions with well-defined reference planes. Those provide simple means for calibration using well established metrology.

However, newer versions of IEC 61850-9-2 for compliant digital substation environment suggest the use of IEEE1588-2008, PTPv2, for synchronization [1]. So far, no widely applicable calibration methods are available.

The timing related goals of this project are

- Establish new calibration model compatible with IEEE1588-2008/2019
- provide traceability to the SI -system via NMI references to PTP devices and timing formats in applications requiring documentation of capabilities as CMCs
- provide reliable and accurate calibrations to unify time synchronization using message based timing and traditional pulse per second signals

This paper is intended as a brief introduction to the “Good Practice guide for the calibration of digital substation instrumentation using PTPv2 timing” [5], which summarizes the project’s results for the timing related objectives and gives advice on suitable calibration practices.

Fig. 1. Generic delays of a network time stamping device. The time stamping points of the device t'_e and t'_i are inaccessible with individual ingress and egress delays with respect to an accessible time reference plane defined by t_e and t_i . The general assumption of symmetry can be expressed by t_d , whereas the asymmetric path is described as unknown t_a .

II. METHODS/RESULTS

IEEE1588-2008 applies a classic two-way time transfer scheme for time synchronization, where a symmetric communication path is assumed. The protocol recognizes `ingressLatency` and `egressLatency` as cause for asymmetry and stipulates the correction of time stamps at all endpoints. Endpoint independent path asymmetries are summarized as `delayAsymmetry` for a specific peer-to-peer connection and if known, the `meanPathDelay` estimates shall be corrected for this term. The IEEE1588-2008 standard does neither provide any provision for handling latencies and asymmetries, nor does it indicate how to determine those errors. However, IEEE-1588-2019 [2appN] defines optional datasets for those values and has an informative appendix on calibration procedures which are based on the White Rabbit calibration procedure [6].

As the PTP protocol implements multi-message exchange and has non-accessible time stamp points, the unknown ingress and egress delays in PTP devices require new calibration methods. In the following three methods are briefly introduced.

A. Absolute Calibration

In absolute calibration [7], the PTP master clock time stamping error is related to an external time reference (one-pulse-per-second, 1PPS) by determining the timing of event type messages as they leave the device.

Referring to Fig. 1, the time stamping available to the PTP protocol at points¹ t'_e and t'_i within the network device are not accessible, and `ingressLatency` and `egressLatency` separate those from a timing reference plane which can be established at an optical or an electrical connector. The latencies are characterized by a common mode delay t_d and an asymmetry term t_a .

$$t_e = t'_e + \text{egressLatency} = t'_e + t_a + t_d$$

$$t_i = t'_i - \text{ingressLatency} = t'_i + t_a - t_d$$

Fig. 3. Generic absolute calibration setup. A monitoring TAP device is used to deterministically replicate the layer 1 data stream to a digitizer that timely records the information present on the wire with respect to a reference time represented by a 1PPS pulse. Timing ambiguities beyond the one second level are resolved by NTP synchronization of the data logger used.

¹ For Ethernet the timestamp point is defined at the Start of Frame (SOF) delimiter of an Ethernet frame.

Fig. 2. Monitoring taps for 100BASE-TX (left) and 100BASE-FX (right). Custom made devices were developed during the project.

Fig. 3 depicts a typical setup for determining the respective master and slave latencies. Using monitoring TAP devices, e.g. Fig. 2, accessible reference planes are created, that deterministically define the boundary between the PTP node and the network and allow to measure PTP event message's timestamp points.

In a PTP master clock, a time-critical event-type Sync message is sent by the master and a master port calibration is performed by comparing the time the Sync message is transmitted with what the master clock claims as its transmission time. A fast, deep-memory oscilloscope is used as a digitizer to record the 1PPS signal together with Layer 1 data at the network interface. The method is primarily implemented for 100BASE-X which is extensively used in digital substations. The digitizer records 125Mcps NRZI line code with 625 MHz sampling, that is 1.6 ns quantization. The necessary post processing to extract PTP timing information is a tedious task and includes MLT3 line decoding and descrambling (100BASE-TX), NRZI decoding, 4B/5B decoding and consecutive frame search, a functionality that a typical network interface device would implement, however with a deterministic, repeatable and accessible timing. In this process the timestamp for a frame is estimated based on the location of the SOF delimiter. The recovered and time tagged Ethernet frames are then, depending on the PTP profile used, subject to further IP decoding (Layer 3 based PTP) and extraction of the

TABLE I. TIME STAMPS AND DELAY SOURCES OF THE SETUP

TS	Source of delay
$t_{L,1}$	Link delay from master port to TAP, no asymmetry
$t_{L,2}$	Link delay from TAP to slave clock, no asymmetry
t_1	TAP delay from network connector input to tapping point
t_2	TAP delay from tapping point to network connection output
t_3	TAP delay from tapping point to output coaxial connector
t_4	cable or probe delay from TAP coaxial output to digitizer
t_5	delay from 1PPS drive to digitizer and reference device 1PPS input

event type message contents. Master timing $t_{m,e}$ $t'_{m,e}$ is retrieved from the *Sync* message, and in case of a two-step exchange, from the `preciseOriginTimestamp` data of a subsequent *Follow-Up* message. To extract master ingress time stamps the capture of *Peer Delay* messages are used to extract $t_{m,i}$, and $t'_{m,i}$ timing. Slave side timing as $t_{s,i}$, and $t'_{s,i}$ can be similarly extracted if the Master communicates *Peer Delay Requests* to the slave. IEC/IEEE 61850-9-3:2016 specifies the Utility Profile, which facilitates those measurements. Using the SOF delays $t_{i,d}$ and $t'_{i,d}$, derived from the frame search, to the reference 1PPS, the respective master and slave traceable time stamps can be calculated as

$$t_i = t_{i,d} + t_{L,x} + t_1 - t_3 - t_4$$

and

$$t_e = t_{e,d} - t_{L,x} - t_1 - t_3 - t_4.$$

Estimation of t_d and t_a on either side of a link is then straight forward by

$$t_d = \frac{(t_e - t'_e) + (t_i - t'_i)}{2} \quad \text{and}$$

$$t_a = \frac{(t_e - t'_e) - (t_i - t'_i)}{2}.$$

Statistics are taken over several message exchanges which are also used to estimate the quality of synchronization between *master* and *slave*² which impact the calibration results. The expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainty for the absolute error is in the order of 10 ns, mostly owing to the calibration uncertainty of network TAP device delays including unknown cabling asymmetries. Further, for the measurement on a 100BASE-X physical layer presented here, the single error readings have discrete values spaced at nominal 8 ns intervals due to 100 Mbit links operating with 125 MHz clock frequency.

Obviously, the same approach can be used for other physical layers, provided that appropriate TAP devices can be constructed and characterized. On Ethernet (IEEE 802.3) higher line rates, such as 1000BASE and higher, may be of interest in the future. This would imply sampling devices in the order of 5 Gs/s to start with and require much more potent processing. The BASE-Tx variants are also difficult to handle as data transport is more complex on several lanes. Thus, the following variant of attacking the sampling and processing problem may be of interest.

B. Absolute calibration using the Linux kernel timing APIs

The digitizer and its necessary post processed decoding logic can be replaced by a modern network interface, utilizing the functionality of the Linux timing APIs. The approach offers use of COTS hardware, is easy to use, and has the flexibility to

Fig. 4. Absolute calibration setup using COTS network hardware. The digitizer is now replaced by modern network interfaces which implement physical clocks for time stamping both network traffic and external events. On systems that support PTM a lossless time transfer between PTM capable devices, e.g. the system clock and network clocks, can effortlessly be implemented. The figure depicts a setup with three NICs, one for capturing and management and two for capturing the Rx and Tx path respectively.

interface *any* physical layer and speed available on hardware time tagging commercial products supported by Linux.

Linux timing infrastructure offers access to physical hardware clocks (PHC) on Ethernet interfaces and allows time stamping of Ethernet frames as well as external events in the form of 1PPS representations of a traceable timescale. Together with an active or passive TAP device the Ethernet frame data is collected using for instance a PCAP [8] based application that integrates timing management, traffic capture and extracts frame time stamping and the content of the relevant PTP messages. Ingress/egress delay determination is the same as in the discrete capture of data traffic described above.

Using shared PHCs on network cards with several interfaces (e.g. Intel E810-xxvda2) or PCIe Precision Time Measurements (PTM [9]) (e.g. Intel i226, Xeon gen4+) the timing of frames for the Rx and Tx taps can be compared with low uncertainty in the synchronization of PHC clocks involved.

The method has many practical advantages but suffers from difficulties determining the TAP related delays $t_{1..5}$, as shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1. TAPs should be passive, such as optical splitters, but for twisted pair interfaces faster than 100BASE, active monitoring TAPs are the only feasible option. As the time stamp points of the Rx and Tx paths are not directly accessible, the estimation of t_5 , with possibly different values t_{5Rx} and t_{5Tx} , requires a calibrated PTP source, such as a White Rabbit Grand Master, to be used to calibrate the setup. Thus, uncertainties of this convenient approach are significant higher than the oscilloscope method and can be determined to be about 50 ns, which is still sufficient for the application of digital substations, and possibly many other uses. On the other hand, most modern Ethernet physical layers variants can easily be accessed with the same methodology, up to 10GBASE-T and 25GBASE-xR can be demonstrated. A typical use case for this method is the calibration and monitoring of high capacity NTP services close to the backbone of a network [9].

² The authors are aware of the problematic PTP master/slave terminology and do not use it in any other aspect.

Fig. 5. Relative calibration setup using a calibration pair. This method expands the delay model and estimates individual ingress and egress delays for clock servo and timing message units. Asymmetry of transmission lines is separated from device asymmetry.

C. Relative calibration

In addition to the absolute PTP clock calibration methods, which record the time difference between the PTP timing message and the PPS for each PTP clock, a relative PTP clock calibration method is proposed as an alternative calibration approach.

Pairs of master/slave PTP devices can be characterized to provide individual calibrations of PTP DUCs [5]. Fig. 5 shows the principal setup of this approach. The method expands the traditional P2P delay model, Fig. 6, by separating ingress and egress delays for timestamps and time pulses, and the delay asymmetry for the device and the propagation link, making calibration of the PTP device pair independent from the link.

For this relative model two reference planes are defined: a) the PTP reference plane where a PTP time stamp is marked by detecting the SOC, and b) the pulse reference plane which is the output pulse signal port. For a golden pair, two PTP clocks in the master-slave hierarchy are defined as the PTP clocks for calibration. A communication path between the pair is setup and synchronization is established. With the help of `meanPathDelay` and `offsetFromMaster` values retrieved from the devices by appropriate means (e.g. SNMP), as well as external phase comparison on the pulse signals available on the devices, presenting accessible reference planes, the total internal latency and relative PTP time offset of the two PTP clocks in the pair are calibrated.

Fig. 6. Extended P2P link delay model used in relative calibration.

The calibration results indicate that the expanded total uncertainty is within 20 ns, where the 1σ type A uncertainty is approximately 5 ns and 1σ type B uncertainty contributes 5~10 ns.

In order to calibrate communication paths (TP cables and fibers) and to verify PTP timing, calibration kits were designed. These are available as an independent tool to verify the accuracy of the PTP timestamps generated by the PTP clocks pair in calibration. Below a SFP version for use with fiber optic modules is shown:

The advantage of the relative method is its ease of use and that it does not need to physically probe the communication path. It is further in line with the current White Rabbit calibration model, allowing a future unified calibration method for regular PTP devices and WR devices (IEEE1588-2019 [2]).

III. COMPARISON

Fig. 8 depicts the setup used for comparing the absolute method with the relative approach using a pair of Meinberg M1000 HPS systems as a Golden Pair. In order to be compatible with the oscilloscope method, the communication path between the devices was restricted to 100BASE-Tx and timing of the digitizer was sourced by the slave timing.

Fig. 7 shows an example of the estimated time differences between the pair, denoted clock1 and clock2, in synchronization when master-slave roles are exchanged. Agreement between absolute and relative estimates are in the order of a few ns which is well covered by the individual uncertainties stated.

Link master	Clock 1		Clock 2	
	Clock 1	Clock 2	Clock 1	Clock 2
Error vs. master 1PPSoutput	-6.3	-0.3	1.1	-3.4
Residual asymmetry	5.3	7.0	3.6	2.2
Slave to master difference calculated from probed data		-8.5	-3.6	
Error vs. own 1PPSoutput	-6.3	-4.8	-5.1	-3.4
OffsetFromMaster		0.8	-7.5	
stdev for all numbers better than 5 ns				

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THE METHODS

Method	Unc	Pros	Cons
Absolute.coax	10 ns	Accuracy, no DUC access necessary	100BASE only
Absolute.tux	50 ns	Any BASE and layer, high packet capacity	Accuracy
Relative.pair	20 ns	Ease of use, WR methodology	Access to DUC

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Calibration of network time is an unproven metrological concept. Two different main methods have been presented that allow to calibrate PTP devices with the Utility Profile to better than 100 ns. Absolute and relative approaches agree well and are good complements for field calibrations. Table 2 briefly summarizes the methods. Formal methods will be prepared by the involved NMIs and will be submitted to RMO EURAMET, and after successful review CMCs will be established [12]. In the future, calibration services may be established by the NMIs.

Future work includes the expansion of the approaches to other network protocols or uses, such NTP or any arbitrary message-based time distribution.

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Fig. 8. Setup for the comparison of the oscilloscope based absolute method with the relative method on a golden pair consisting of two Meinberg M1000 with HPS PTP cards.

Fig. 7. Slave to master clock difference between the pair of M1000 HPS cards in master-slave configuration, top plot clock1 master, and bottom with clock2 as master. Visible 8 ns bands are due to the fast pulling of the local HPS oscillator to discrete timing of the 125 MHz network clock of the 100BASE link. The wander in phase reflects the synchronization loop of the Meinberg master clock to its 1PPS reference.

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